

EXAMINING THE LEVELS OF AWARENESS AND ACCEPTANCE OF GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TO SUPPLEMENT PROBLEM-SOLVING ANALYSIS IN AN AEROSPACE COMPANY

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ABSTRACT

In the chosen aerospace manufacturing company, engineers have a problem in efficiently identifying root causes and determining effective corrective actions. The absence of immediate yet informative insights contribute to this problem. This research examined the levels of awareness and acceptance of Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) in problem-solving analysis. With the identified awareness and acceptance levels, measures were identified to effectively use Generative AI to supplement problem-solving analysis. This research used Davis' Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to identify factors influencing the effective implementation and usage of new technologies such as Generative AI. A descriptive research design, using quantitative method, was used to support the objectives of the research. Data were gathered through survey questionnaire and was analyzed through comparison of means. This research has revealed that the engineers of the chosen aerospace manufacturing company have a high level of awareness regarding Generative AI. Additionally, it also revealed a high level of acceptance among engineers of the chosen aerospace company of Generative AI in supplementing their problem-solving. These levels of awareness and acceptance have helped in the identification of effective measures for utilizing Generative AI in problem-solving analysis. These measures include establishing a framework, establishing a review process, cultivating a proficient workforce, and developing and pursuing other potential uses of Generative AI.

Keywords: *Generative AI, Problem-Solving Analysis, Aerospace Manufacturing Companies*

INTRODUCTION

Nature and Scope of the Problem Investigated

Today's manufacturing companies operate in a highly complex and dynamic environment. This requires engineers to be knowledgeable on a wide range of topics in order to solve problems. While the 8D and 3C problem solving methodologies can provide a structured process in problem-solving analysis, engineers still encounter difficulties. A problem observed on the chosen aerospace manufacturing company is the lack of immediate but informative insights that lead to inefficient and ineffective problem-solving analysis. Moreover, time constraints and resource limitations can impede the thorough execution of the problem-solving methodologies potentially leading to ineffective corrective actions.

Currently, Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) models such as ChatGPT are establishing themselves as new and innovative technology. It can provide information, answer questions, and engage in discussions on a wide range of subjects, even on the topics and tools related to manufacturing, quality management systems, and problem-solving analysis. Although Generative AI can be advantageous in modern-day manufacturing, it is important to thoroughly evaluate its application and consider how it is accepted by engineers in the chosen aerospace manufacturing company.

Review of Pertinent Literature

According to studies by Cahyo et al. (2020) and Elangovan et al. (2020), effective problem-solving analysis is crucial for reducing defects and waste in production and improving customer satisfaction. However, while problem-solving methodologies have been successful in various industries, challenges such as lack of expertise, employee bias, and miscommunication exist (Bokrantz et al., 2020). Incorporating emerging technologies like Generative AI, which offers human-like responses, can improve problem-solving analysis through its decision-making capabilities according to a report by Northwest (2023).

Manufacturing organizations benefit from the use and application of Generative AI. In an article published by Casidsid et al. (2023), Generative AI can be used in document management, logistics optimization, preventive maintenance, and compliance identification in manufacturing

Generative AI, such as ChatGPT, provides user with human-like responses drawn from statistical patterns of language in vast datasets on the internet. As Generative AI and ChatGPT continues to evolve and improve, impressive results in the years to come are expected (Kalla & Smith, 2023). Various sectors, including manufacturing, are now exploring the use of ChatGPT.

Wilson (2023) provided a step-by-step method on how to use ChatGPT in problem-solving analysis.

1. Identify the problem to be solved using Chat-GPT. Be specific as possible and provide relevant details that will help ChatGPT understand the problem.
2. Review the response from ChatGPT. Ensure that it addresses the problem. If the response does not fully address the problem, generate again a response from ChatGPT.
3. Follow-up questions.
4. Seek additional resources.

While it is beneficial, the applications of ChatGPT are met with mixed reaction from different sectors. Furthermore, as reported by the United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission (US NRC), understanding Generative AI requires consideration on safety, control, and security.

Although it's met with cautious optimism in healthcare and varied performance in education and research, supply chain and manufacturing industries show enthusiasm for its benefits such as logistics optimization and workforce training (Gabashvili, 2023). However, concerns about AI's impact on employment and society requires a strategic approach to its implementation (Gabashvili, 2023). Overall, the use of Generative AI in problem-solving analysis holds promise for improving efficiency.

Research Framework

The research input focused on the awareness and acceptance levels of engineers of the chosen aerospace manufacturing company in using Generative AI in supplementing their problem-solving analysis. These were further supported by the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use of Generative AI in problem-solving analysis. These data were gathered via a survey questionnaire based on Davis's Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). These data were vital in determining the measures that will guide the chosen aerospace manufacturing company to effectively supplement problem-solving analysis with Generative AI. Based on the results and gathered literatures, this research came up with measures and strategies to effectively use Generative AI in problem-solving analysis.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Research Questions

This research determined and provided answers to the following research problems and objectives:

1. The awareness level of engineers of the chosen aerospace manufacturing company on Generative AI;
2. The acceptance level of engineers of the chosen aerospace manufacturing company on Generative AI; and
3. The measures that can be recommended to the chosen aerospace manufacturing company to effectively use Generative AI in supplementing their problem-solving analysis.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research used a quantitative research design which supported the defined objectives. The primary data were composed of the engineers' awareness, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and acceptance on the use of Generative AI in problem-solving analysis. These data were collected to aid in identifying the measures needed to effectively use Generative AI in problem-solving analysis.

Research Locale

The research was conducted on the chosen aerospace manufacturing company in the Philippines. The participants held engineering positions and came from different departments, including quality, manufacturing/ process, and design engineering. These departments are actively involved in conducting problem-solving analysis.

Population and Sampling Design

The respondents were of legal working age and currently employed in the chosen manufacturing company in the Philippines. The chosen departments participated on this research are those with experience and knowledge in resolving manufacturing issues through problem-solving analysis. The sample size was identified using quota sampling and approval from the chosen aerospace manufacturing company's human resources department were sought. 30 engineers from design, manufacturing, and quality were identified for this research.

Research Instruments

Quantitative research design was used for this research. A standardized instrument, via a survey questionnaire, was used to collect the primary data. The survey was into 2 parts, engineers' awareness on Generative AI and acceptance, which also factors the perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and attitude, towards use of Generative AI in problem-

solving analysis. The validated set of questions were constructed based on Davis' Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Framework and the research's conceptual framework.

Data Gathering Procedure

The primary data used on this research were collected via a survey questionnaire. The data gathering process was performed with the company's consent and approval. The survey included questions gauging the awareness and acceptance level in using Generative AI in supplementing problem-solving analysis through 5-point Likert scale (5 being the highest and 1 being the lowest).

Management and Treatment of Data

To analyze the data obtained from the survey, descriptive statistics were employed. This statistical method helped produce a comprehensive summarization of the survey responses, aiding in the identification of awareness and acceptance levels among the engineers of the chosen aerospace manufacturing company. Specifically, the comparison of means was used to delve deeper into the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Awareness on AI and Generative AI

Based on the collected data shown in Table 1, the design engineering department expressed a high level of awareness of 3.60 on Generative AI. Meanwhile, the quality engineering department also expressed a high level of awareness of 4.10 on Generative AI. Lastly, the manufacturing department exhibited a high level of awareness of 3.80. With an overall awareness level of 3.83, the chosen aerospace manufacturing company have a high level of awareness on Generative AI. This collective awareness is indicative of a good foundation for potential integration and use of Generative AI in the chosen aerospace manufacturing company.

Table 1. Awareness Level of Different Departments on Generative AI

Department	Awareness Level (Mean)	Verbal Interpretation
Design	3.60	High level
Manufacturing	3.80	High level
Quality	4.10	High level
Overall Rating	3.83	High level

Acceptance of use of Generative AI to supplement Problem-solving Analysis

Table 2 presented the perceived usefulness, ease of use, attitude, and acceptance towards use Generative AI in problem-solving analysis.

Table 2. Overall Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and Perceived Attitude towards use of Generative AI in problem-solving analysis

	Overall Rating (Mean)	Verbal Interpretation
Level of Perceived Usefulness (Root Cause Analysis)	3.80	High level of perceived usefulness of Generative AI in improving the accuracy of finding the root cause.
Level of Perceived Usefulness (Corrective Action)	3.87	High level of perceived usefulness of Generative AI in the effective identification of corrective action/s.
Level of Perceived Usefulness (Overall Problem-solving Analysis)	3.83	High level of Perceived Usefulness of Generative AI in overall problem-solving analysis
Level of Perceived Ease of Use (Learning Generative AI)	3.83	High level of perceived ease of learning to use Generative AI
Level of Perceived Ease of Use (Learning Curve)	3.67	High level of perceived significant learning curve in using Generative AI in problem-solving analysis
Level of Perceived Ease of Use (Becoming Proficient)	3.83	High level of perceived ease of becoming proficient in using Generative AI in problem-solving analysis
Level of Attitude Towards Use of Generative AI (As a Positive Experience)	4.13	High level of attitude towards the use of Generative AI in problem-solving analysis as positive experience
Level of Attitude Towards Use of Generative AI (As Beneficial)	3.83	High level of attitude towards the use of Generative AI as a beneficial tool in problem-solving analysis
Level of Acceptance	3.93	High level of acceptance in using Generative AI to supplement problem-solving analysis

Across the board, Generative AI was highly regarded for its perceived usefulness in improving problem-solving analysis (mean rating of 3.83). Specifically, it is seen as particularly valuable in root cause analysis (mean rating of 3.80) and in the effective identification of corrective actions (mean rating of 3.87). This perception can be traced back from the Generative AI's capacity to analyze complex datasets, identify patterns, and generate insights that can contribute to a more accurate understanding of provided issues (Kalla & Smith, 2023).

While Generative AI is perceived useful, it was acknowledged that there is a high level of learning curve in using it in problem-solving analysis (mean rating of 3.67). Despite this, engineers expressed a high level of perceived ease of learning Generative AI in problem-solving analysis (mean rating of 3.83) and a high level of perceived ease of becoming proficient in using Generative AI in problem-solving analysis (mean rating of 3.83). This data emphasized that proficiency in the use of Generative AI in problem-solving analysis is easy and attainable.

The data also reflected a high level of attitude towards the use of Generative AI in problem-solving analysis as positive experience (mean rating of 4.13) and as a beneficial tool in problem-solving analysis (mean rating of 3.83). This collective mindset signifies the engineers' recognition of Generative AI as a beneficial tool for effectively addressing and analyzing problems within the chosen aerospace manufacturing company

Ultimately, the collected data emphasized an inclination and acceptance to adopt Generative AI in problem-solving analysis (mean rating of 3.93). It further recognized the collective perception of engineers of the chosen aerospace manufacturing company based on its usefulness, ease of use, and overall attitude towards its integration into problem-solving processes.

Measures to effectively supplement problem-solving analysis practices with Generative AI

Establishing effective measures to effectively use Generative AI in problem-solving analysis is important and it can be affected by engineers' awareness and acceptance. Drawing from research findings and existing literature, the study outlined the four key measures illustrated in Figure 2. The first goal focused on establishing an organizational framework for Generative AI usage, aligning with recommendations from the US NRC and Wilson (2023) to ensure seamless integration. The framework, shown in Figure 3, can guide engineers on the process of problem identification. The second goal emphasized the need for a review process while using Generative AI. The third goal highlighted the importance of cultivating a proficient workforce through trainings. Lastly, the fourth goal highlighted the need for organizations to explore and leverage the full potential of Generative AI across various applications, fostering a culture of innovation and continuous improvement within the chosen aerospace manufacturing company.

Figure 2. Measures in Implementing Generative AI into the Workforce

Figure 3. Framework - Use of Generative AI to Supplement Problem Solving Analysis

Summary of Findings

The awareness level of engineers (30 from design, manufacturing, and quality department) on Generative AI yielded 3.83. This conveyed a message that the engineers have a high level of awareness on Generative AI. Furthermore, the acceptance level of engineers in using Generative AI yielded 3.93. This conveyed a message that the engineers accept the use of Generative AI to supplement their problem-solving analysis. These are further supported by their general and positive response on perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and attitude towards use of Generative AI to supplement their problem-solving analysis. Lastly, the measures to ensure effective implementation includes formulating a strategic plan that includes establishing a framework, establishing a review process, cultivating proficient workforce, and developing and pursuing other applications of Generative AI in the organization.

Conclusions

It was concluded that the engineers of the chosen aerospace manufacturing company have high level of awareness on Generative AI. This collective awareness on Generative AI is indicative of a good foundation for potential integration and use of Generative AI in the chosen aerospace manufacturing company. Additionally, engineers accept the use of Generative AI in supplementing the problem-solving analysis of the chosen aerospace manufacturing company. Although new and might pose some challenges, engineers are in favor of using Generative AI to supplement problem-solving analysis. This acceptance is indicative of openness among engineers to adapt the measures to be provided to ensure effective use of Generative AI in supplementing the problem-solving analysis of the chosen aerospace manufacturing company. Furthermore, the identified measures are vital in improving problem-solving analysis with Generative AI. This includes establishing a framework suitable to the autonomy level of Generative AI in problem-solving analysis. This will also serve as guidance in using Generative AI as a supplementary tool in problem-solving analysis. This may also be supported by establishing a review process to ensure effectiveness of the process. This plan also highlighted the need for a training program that will help cultivate a proficient workforce. Lastly, as part of continuous improvement, pursue other potential applications of Generative AI.

Recommendations

This research determined the opportunities for future, similar, or related research such as the study of Generative AI and problem-solving analysis. Future study can also be done not just in the chosen aerospace manufacturing company but also in other companies outside Philippines. Similar studies may also be conducted outside the aerospace industry such as automotive, medical, and other industry that uses problem-solving

analysis. This will yield participation of more employees in the survey and will even result in a more remarkable result.

The study could still be improved by including more engineers and employees who are familiar with problem-solving analysis, methodologies, and practices. Moreover, future researchers can use other types of research methods, such as qualitative or mixed methods, to improve the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As part of the data collection process, the following ethical considerations were observed to ensure confidentiality and integrity.

Voluntary participation. Respondents participated on the survey with their full consent and were not forced. The brief purpose of the research and survey were explained to them through an introductory letter. Respondents have the right to withdraw from any participation on this research at any time if they wish to do so.

Confidentiality. The data collection process strictly followed Republic Act No. 10173, otherwise known as the Data Privacy Act, to protect all forms of information, be it private, personal, or sensitive, provided by the respondents.

Potential for Harm. Respondents were assured that they will not be subjected to any kind of harm, may it be physical, psychological, or emotional. The survey focused only on the aspects of research questions and objectives, and they were protected from any uncomfortable questions.

Communication. The objectives of this research were communicated in a clear and concise manner prior the respondents partaking in the survey. All communications, including inquiries and clarifications, are documented.

Data findings, discussion, and analysis. Primary data findings from the survey were used as intended. Objectivity in discussions and analyses were observed throughout the research that ensured no misleading information and biased representation were drawn from this research.

Acknowledgement of works. The works and citations by other authors referenced in this research were acknowledged following APA format.

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